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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
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05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
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05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
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05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
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08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
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08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE REGIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE INDUSTRY OF NAVAI REGION

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Abstract. This article deeply studies the current state of utilization of production potential in the development of industry in the regions of Navoi region and the possibilities of its effective use. The results of the article are of great importance in improving the regional development strategy of industry, in the formation of economic planning and investment policy.

Keywords: regional development, industrial potential, productive resources, economic reforms, macroeconomic stability, gross domestic product, structural structure, industrial policy, statistical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The region was first established on 20.04.1982 and existed in this status until 1988. It was later re-established on 27 January 1992. Its area is 111.0 thousand square kilometers, which is approximately one-quarter of the territory of the republic. The population is 1,094.7 thousand people, accounting for 4.0% of the country's total population.¹ Interestingly, these geographical indicators demonstrate a strong spatial contrast within Uzbekistan. In terms of area and demographic potential, the region ranks second in the country. However, by territory, it is second after the Republic of Karakalpakstan, while in terms of population size it is ahead only of Syrdarya region, i.e., second from the bottom. These comparative indicators confirm the extremely low population density in Navoi region.

The internal administrative structure of the region is not complex; there are only 8 rural districts. It should be noted that Syrdarya region also has 8 such administrative units, but its territory is 23.2 times smaller than Navoi region. Therefore, rural districts in Navoi cover very large areas, indicating weak territorial development and limited economic capacity.

Indeed, in Uchkuduk district this indicator reaches 46.6 thousand sq. km, and in Tomdi district 42.5 thousand sq. km. In this respect, after Qo'ng'iro't district of Karakalpakstan (76.0 thousand sq. km), they rank second and third in the country. These two districts alone occupy 80.3% of Navoi region and nearly one-fifth of the country's total area.

The difference between the smallest district (Karmana) and the largest (Uchkuduk) is 49.1 times. Konimex district has a unique geographical position: its administrative center is separated from the main territory, and the remaining part can be considered an exclave.

Karmana and Nurota districts are among the earliest established administrative units of this category in Uzbekistan. Before the formation of Navoi region, the southern districts—Kyzyltepa, Karmana, Navbahor—belonged to Bukhara region, while Xatirchi and Nurota were part of Samarkand region. Uchkuduk and Tomdi were once under the jurisdiction of Karakalpakstan.

Navoi region is specialized in the territorial division of labor of the republic mainly in mining, especially non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical and construction materials industries, as well as livestock farming focused on meat-wool production. Its share in the national economy includes: 5.4% of GDP, 11.2% of industrial production, 4.2% of agricultural output, 47.0% of investment volume, 3.6% of retail trade turnover, and 2.8% of paid services. In exports its share is 4.2%, and in imports 3.8%.

Navoi region is located in the central and northern part of Uzbekistan. It shares a long border with

1 Uralov E.O. Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot o'quv qo'llanma // Toshkent 2023 –yil 89 bet

Kazakhstan. It also borders Bukhara region in the west, Samarkand and partially Jizzakh regions in the south and southeast, Karakalpakstan in the north and northwest, and a short border with Kashkadarya region in the south.

Geographically, the region has a distinctive territorial configuration. Its main population, economic activity, and processing industries are concentrated in the relatively small southern part, while the central and northern areas are sparsely populated desert zones characterized by extensive pastoral livestock farming and mining activities. Borders in many areas are almost straight, which is typical for poorly developed desert regions such as Karakalpakstan, and countries like Chad, Sudan, and Canada.

Navoi region differs significantly from other regions in its orographic structure. It includes small residual mountains, while lowlands are located in the northern and northwestern parts (Kyzylkum desert), and depressions such as Mingbuloq, Malali, and Karatov are found in the interior. Elevations range from 250–300 meters above sea level, while the highest peaks reach around 1800 meters in the Oqtov range.

The Nurota, Oqtov, and Karatov ranges connect with the Turkestan and Zarafshan mountains in the south and southeast. These mountains are rich in mineral resources. Important residual mountains include Bo'kantov, Yetimtog', Tomditov, Aytimtov, Ko'kpatas, Qozoqtoq, Quljuqtoq, Beltov, and Ovminzatov. The highest point of the region is Avga Peak in Nurota Mountains (1701 m).

Most of the terrain consists of deserts and sandy areas such as Qorakota, Mulali, Mingbuloq, Pikaturma, and Yomonqum. In spring, these areas are covered with green vegetation and tulips, creating a beautiful landscape.

The region is rich in mineral resources, especially gold, uranium, phosphorites, asbestos, feldspar, marble, and construction materials. These resources play a key role in shaping the regional economy and export potential.

The climate is extremely dry and continental, with annual precipitation of only 100–200 mm, which limits agricultural development. Therefore, the region is mainly specialized in pasture livestock farming, especially Karakul sheep breeding.

Hydrographic resources are poorly developed. The Zarafshan River significantly decreases in flow near Navoi city. Reservoirs such as Kuyimozor, Sho'rkul, and Tudakul have been constructed to support irrigation. Canals such as Amu-Bukhara, Ortao'chol, and Konimex also exist.

The long north–south extension of the region and the location of its administrative center in the southern periphery create challenges in socio-economic development, especially in transport infrastructure and service delivery.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, improving the territorial structure of industry and the development of new technologies have enabled faster and more accurate macroeconomic forecasting for regions. This direction is recognized as a priority in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In particular, the Presidential Decree PQ-52 dated 10 February 2023, "On additional measures for the comprehensive socio-economic development of Navoi region in 2023–2024 and improving the living standards of the population" plays an important role in developing productive forces, rational use of labor resources, and addressing social issues [1].

Balanced industrial development across regions, including expansion of enterprises not only in Navoi city but also in Konimex, Nurota, and Xatirchi districts, is emphasized [2]. Studies analyze differences in industrial output across districts and propose measures to reduce territorial disparities.

In addition, A.M. Sodiqov doctoral dissertation "Socio-economic development of regions of Uzbekistan and mechanisms of its regulation" examines regional development processes and their regulatory mechanisms [3].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology for improving the territorial structure of the industry of Navoi region The industrial sector occupies an important place in the economy of Navoi region. For the effective development of industry in the region and the improvement of its territorial structure, it is important to use a scientifically based research methodology. The research methodology helps to analyze the location of the industry by region, the level of development and existing opportunities.

The main goal of this study is to study the territorial location of industrial sectors in Navoi region, identify existing problems and develop scientifically based proposals for improving the territorial structure of the industry. To achieve this goal, a number of scientific research methods are used.

In the research process, analysis and synthesis methods are used first of all. The analysis method studies individual sectors of the regional industry, production volume, number of enterprises and their location by region. The synthesis method allows you to summarize the data obtained and draw final conclusions.

Also, the statistical method is important in the study. This method analyzes indicators such as the volume of industrial production in Navoi region, the composition of sectors, and the level of development in the regions. Based on statistical data, the dynamics of regional development of industry are determined. In addition, the comparative method compares the level of industrial development between the districts of Samarkand region. This helps to determine which regions have high or low industrial development.

The research also uses the cartographic method. This method shows the territorial location of industrial enterprises using maps. As a result, industrial centers, industrial zones, and production areas are identified.

Also, the systematic approach method studies the interrelationship of industry with transport, raw material base, labor resources, and infrastructure. This method allows for a comprehensive analysis of factors affecting industrial development. The main sources of information for the study are data from the State Statistics Committee data from the Navoi Regional Statistics Department, scientific literature, and economic research results.

The main sources of information for the study are data from the State Statistics Committee, data from the Navoi Regional Statistics Department, scientific literature, and economic research results.

As a result, practical proposals will be developed to further improve the territorial structure of industry in the Navoi region, establish new industrial zones, and accelerate regional economic development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

1-table

Main economic indicators of Navoi region (billion soums) data for 2020-2025²

№	District and city	Industrial products billion soums	In percent	Industrial products billion soums	In percent
		2020 yil		2025 yil	
1	Navoi region	65 084,9	100	189350,9	100
2	Navoi city	54 997,2	84,5	166 715,4	88,0
3	Zarafshan city	316,0	0,5	1 067,9	0,6
4	G'ozg'on city			275,9	0,1
5	districts:				
6	Karmana district	6 950,4	10,1	13 580,5	7,2
7	Konimex district	137,9	0,2	972,1	0,5
8	Kyzyltepa district	1 131,0	1,7	2 030,8	1,1
9	Navbahor district	500,4	0,7	1 401,6	0,7
10	Nurota district	265,0	0,4	650,9	0,3
11	Tomdi district	37,3	0,05	99,7	0,05
12	Uchkuduk district	175,9	0,3	701,3	0,4
13	Xatirchi district	573,8	0,9	1 854,8	1,0

Source: data from the Navoi regional statistics committee

Overall growth analysis 2020 65 084,9 billion soums 2025 189 350,9 billion soums growth Absolute +124, 266 billion soums Relative growth of almost 2,9 times conclusion Industry in Navoi region has developed very rapidly. This is mainly due to mining and large industrial enterprises.

Analysis by region Navoi city-the absolute leader 2020 84, % 2025 88,0 %, growth 54,997-166,715 billion soums analysis, almost 90 % of the regional industry is located here Industrial concentration is high This shows territorial imbalance Karmana district 2020 10,1 %, 2025 7,2 %, the volume increased, but the share decreased, other regions grew faster, especially Navoi city, other regions have a low share Zarafshan 0,5 %- 0,6 %, stable growth, Kyzyltepa 1,7 %-0,7 % unchanged least developed regions, Tomdi district 0,05 %, Gozgan district 0,1 %, Nurota district 0,3 %, analysis industry is very low There are infrastructure or resource constraints. The fastest growing regions Konimex district 137,9-972,1 (-7times) Uchkuduk district 175,9-701,3 (-4times) Khatirchi district 573,8 -1854,8 (-3 times) Conclusion The main projects is the territorial imbalance in the emergence of new industrial projects in these regions. In 2025 Navoi city will have 88%, and all other

2 Author's development

regions will have 12 %, which is a very large difference.

General conclusion Industry is growing very rapidly in the region But development is uneven, industry is mainly concentrated in Navoi city The industry in the districts is still weak. The most important part of the recommendations is to distribute industry to the regions, open new factories in the districts, develop infrastructure, develop electricity, roads, logistics, develop industry close to resources in places such as Konimeh, Uchkuduk, attract investment, provide incentives to underdeveloped regions.

CONCLUSION AND SUGESTIONS

Improving the territorial structure of the Navoi region's industry is carried out through diversification of the industry, balanced development across districts, attraction of investments and introduction of innovations. This will ensure sustainable growth of the regional economy and employment.

Navoi region is one of the largest industrial regions of Uzbekistan, with developed mining, metallurgy, chemical and energy sectors. Improving the territorial structure involves the balanced placement of industry across districts, efficient use of resources and increasing added value.

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